

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF NASA ARSHA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO NASAL POLYP - A SINGLE CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Nasa is the most important organ of *Pranavaha Srotas*. It is important organ of respiratory system as well as gateway of cranial cavity. *Nasarsha* is one of the *Nasagata Roga* among thirty-one *Nasagata Rogas* mentioned in Ayurveda. *Nasarsha* can be correlated to nasal polyps. Nasal polyps are non-neoplastic prolapsed, pedunculated part of the oedematous mucosa of nose or paranasal sinuses. Prolonged use of antihistamines, decongestants, antibiotics and steroids lead to drug resistance and decrease immunity. Fear of surgery, its complications and cost have restricted many patients from undergoing surgery. Hence the present case study was taken to evaluate the efficacy of *Ksharakarma* in the management of *Nasarshas* with special reference to Nasal Polyp along with internal medications for reducing its recurrence and improve the immunity. *Kshara* is an excellent *Anusastra* in the management of *Arsha*. As it has *Lekhana*, *Tridoshaghna*,

Teekshna and *Ushna* property. Hence A case of *Nasarsha* (nasal polyp) was successfully managed using a combined Ayurvedic approach involving 5 sittings of *Apamarga Kshara* application and internal *Shamana Ausadhis*. The therapy was well tolerated, and no recurrence occurred during follow-up, suggesting that this integrated Ayurvedic regimen offers a safe, minimally invasive, and effective alternative for managing *Nasarsha*.

KEYWORDS: *Nasarsha*, Nasal polyp, *Kshara karma*, *Shamana Aushadi*.

INTRODUCTION

Nasal polyps are benign, oedematous, and inflammatory outgrowths of the nasal or paranasal sinus mucosa, commonly associated with chronic rhinosinusitis, allergic reactions, asthma, and impaired mucociliary clearance. They present clinically with nasal obstruction, reduced sense of smell, nasal discharge, snoring, headache, and compromised quality of life. Globally, the prevalence of nasal polyps ranges from 1–4% of the general population, with higher occurrence in adults above 40 years and in individuals with chronic allergies or asthma.^[1]

Clinical examination reveals single or multiple, smooth, glistening, grape like polypoid masses in the nasal cavity. Polyps can be graded into four Stages according to their size.

- Stage I: Limited to the extent of middle turbinate^[2]
- Stage II: Extending beyond the limit of middle turbinate.
- Stage III: Approaching to inferior turbinate.
- Stage IV: Going up to the floor of nose.

Modern medical management generally includes intranasal corticosteroids, antihistamines, antibiotics, and oral steroids, followed by Functional Endoscopic Sinus Surgery (FESS) in moderate-to-severe cases.^[3] However, surgery carries the risk of recurrence, reported up to 40–60% in chronic inflammatory cases and involves significant financial burden, especially in recurrent or bilateral polyposis. Thus, the need for a safe, economical, and long-term effective alternative approach is increasingly recognized.

In Ayurveda, the condition known as *Nasarsha* is described among the 31 *Nasagata Rogas* by classical texts like the *Sushruta Samhita*.^[4] The term *Arsha* literally implies an outgrowth that causes distress, similar to an enemy (*arivat pranam srñati*).^[5] and when situated in the *Nasa*, it presents as a fleshy mass (*Mamsa Pinda* or *Adhimamsa*) leading to obstruction. The *Samprapti* is primarily attributed to the aggravation of *Kapha Dosha* and *Vata Dosha* and take *Sthana samsraya* in the *Nasa Srotas*, vitiate the *Dushyas* specifically *Twak*, *Mamsa*, and *Medo Dhatu* resulting in the formation of the oedematous mass.^[6] The aggravated *Kapha* creates a sticky, proliferative environment, while deranged *Vata* elevates and pushes the vitiated *Kapha* upward, resulting in polyp-like structures. The presents with *Nasa Avarodha* (nasal obstruction), *Ati Kshavathu* (excessive sneezing), and *Nasa Srava* (nasal discharge) etc strongly align with the clinical presentation of Nasal Polyps.

Ayurveda proposes a holistic, minimally invasive, and cost-effective management strategy using *Kshara karma* and *kapha-vata hara shamana aushadis* that address both disease symptoms and root causative factors. Compared to modern surgical approaches, Ayurvedic therapies require significantly lower financial expenditure, have minimal recurrence rates when followed with proper lifestyle and dietary guidance, and focus on long-term mucosal restoration. Hence, Ayurveda offers a sustainable, affordable, and comprehensive therapeutic model for the management of nasal polyp.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

1. To evaluate the efficacy of Kshara Karma in the management of Nasarshas w.s.r to Nasal polyp.
2. To evaluate the effect of oral Ayurvedic Medicines in the management and prevention of recurrence of Nasarshas w.s.r. to Nasal polyp.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source of Data Patients were selected from the outpatient and inpatient of Shalaky Tantra department from Government Ayurvedic Medical College, Bangalore, Karnataka.

CASE STUDY

Chief Complaints & Associated Complaints: A male patient of age 42 years complaining of bilateral nasal obstruction, recurrent sneezing, heaviness of head, rhinorrhoea, difficulty in breathing during the episodes on and off since 1 year.

History Of Present Illness: A male patient of age 42 years was apparently healthy 1 year back. Gradually he started developing bilateral nasal obstruction on and off, recurrent sneezing on and off, rhinorrhoea on and off, heaviness of head and headache. It was so recurrent that, the patient was feeling difficulty in breathing during the episodes and unable to concentrate on the daily activities. So, he took nasal decongestants and anti-allergic drugs prescribed by one of the allopathy doctor who diagnosed the case as Nasal Polyp on examination. The symptoms used to relief for sometimes but was recurring. So, he was suggested to undergo surgery for nasal polyps. Patient was not willing to get surgery done, so he consulted our hospital for further management.

Past History: History of allergy to dust, smoke, pollens.

Personal History

- a) Appetite-Normal
- b) Bowel-Regular
- c) Micturition-Normal
- d) Sleep-Normal

Family History- Nothing significant

Ashtasthana Pareeksha

Nadi: 78/min

Mala: Regular, twice a day

Mutra: 5-6 times/day

Jihwa: Alpa liptta

Shabda: Prakruta

Sparsha: Prakrutha

Druk: Prakruta

Akruthi: Madhyama

Vitals

Pulse rate-78/min,

Respiratory rate-22/min,

BP-126/84 mm of Hg,

Temp. -Afebrile

Systemic examination: No specific abnormalities detected

Nasal Examination

Inspection -DNS towards Right side

Palpation-Examination of PNS-tenderness present in maxillary, frontal sinus.

Anterior Rhinoscopy- (right nostril) unilateral round, pale, glossy, polypoidal masses in the middle meatus is seen. Insensitive to probing, does not bleed on touch when examined by using Jobsons probe. Bilateral Inferior turbinate hypertrophy.

Investigations: AEC - 550cells/microliter of blood, ESR-30mm/hr.

Samprapti Ghatakas*Dosha – Kaphavata**Dushya - Mamsa, Meda, Asthi**Agni - Jataragni**Udbhava Sthana – Urdhwajatru**Sanchara Sthana - Urdhwajatru**Vyakta Sthana - Nasa**Srotas – Pranavaha**Srotodushti – Sanga**Rogamarga – Bahya**Sadhyasadhyata – Kricchrasadhya***Diagnosis**

The diagnosis was done based on signs and symptoms and examination of Nose, as nasal polyp.

Treatment**Table no 1- Timeline.**

Treatment	Duration
Tab <i>Chirakadi Vati</i> (1-1-1) BF	5days
<i>Avipatikara Choorna</i> (0-0-1tsp) with warm water AF	5days
<i>Apamarga Kshara</i> Application	2 times in a week (5 sittings) =15days
Internally 1) Tab <i>Mahalakshmi vilasa rasa</i> (1-0-1) AF 2) <i>Dashamularista</i> (20ml with 40ml of water) (1-0-1) AF 3) <i>Haridrakhanda</i> (1tsp-01tsp) with warm water BF 4) <i>Asagtyaharitaki rasayana</i> (1tsp -01tsp) with warm water BF	For 15 days

Pathya Apathya (dietary and lifestyle guidelines adviced)

The patient was strictly advised to avoid cold drinks, ice cream, junk food, curd, salad, fruit, fermented food items, and spicy foods. The regular intake of *Shunti Siddha Aushadha Jala* throughout the day was recommended as part of their routine. *Pravat Sevan* (Head wind) *Diwaswapna* (daytime sleeping) should be avoided, and *Goghruta* or *Shikhari Taila* was to be regularly applied to the nasal mucosa to prevent irritation from dust particles.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

Significant reduction in the presenting symptoms of the patient was seen after 3 weeks of treatment with a 3 days interval after 1 month of follow up. The patient's condition showed gradual improvement, assessed through both subjective symptoms and objective findings. A comprehensive evaluation was performed, after completion of therapy.

Table no 2- Observation During Treatment.

	Before treatment	During treatment (3 rd sitting)	1 st follow up (15 th day)	After treatment (30 th day)
Polyp grading	Grade 4	Grade 3	Grade 2	Grade 0

Fig 1: Before treatment.

Fig 2: During treatment.

Fig 3: After treatment.

DISCUSSION

In this study, the combined approach of *Apamarga Khṣara Karma* and internal Ayurvedic medications demonstrated significant therapeutic potential. *Kshara karma* is an excellent *Anushastra* in the management of *Arsha*, with its *Chedana*, *Bhedana*, *Lekhana*, *Tridoshaghna* with *Usna* and *Teekshna* properties, acted as an effective local procedure for reducing the polypoid mass and clearing nasal obstruction with minimal invasiveness. *Kshara* as *Usna* and *Lekhana* property it can reduce the vitiated *dosha* and *dushya*. And also promote the healing of nasal mucosa. *Mahalakṣmi Vilasa Rasa* contributed immunomodulatory and antimicrobial benefits that aided tissue healing with balancing the *dosha* of *Kapha* and *Vata*. *Haridrakhanda* chosen for their potent anti-allergic, anti-inflammatory, and *Kapha-Vata* balancing actions, addressing the systemic allergic and inflammatory components often underlying *Nasarsha*. *Agastyaharitaki Rasayana* offers a vital *Rasayana* (rejuvenating) and respiratory tonic effect, helping to strengthen the entire upper respiratory tract (*Pranavaha Srotas*), clear accumulated mucus (*Kapha*), and boost local immunity. *Chitrakadi Vaṭi* enhanced *Agni* and improved digestion, preventing further *Kapha* buildup, and *Dashamula Ariṣṭa* offered strong anti-inflammatory effects that reduced sinus congestion and post-procedural inflammation. Clinical observations indicated improved airflow, better olfaction, reduced sinusitis episodes, prevent the recurrence of nasal polyp and enhanced overall quality

of life with minimal adverse effects, supporting the relevance of this integrative approach in chronic nasal conditions.

CONCLUSION

The combined use of *Apamarga Khṣara Karma* and selected internal Ayurvedic medications presents an effective, minimally invasive, and holistic treatment strategy for *Nasarhsa*. *Khṣara Karma* successfully reduced the polyp size and improved nasal airflow, while the internal drugs worked systemically to balance doshas, enhance immunity, and reduce chronic inflammation. Together, they produced significant and sustained relief, minimized recurrence tendencies, and supported overall respiratory health. This protocol is cost-effective, well-tolerated, and suitable for outpatient settings.

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